

Epitactic growth of celestite on anhydrite: Substrate induced twinning and morphological evolution of aggregates.

Journal:	<i>CrystEngComm</i>
Manuscript ID	CE-ART-05-2020-000755
Article Type:	Paper
Date Submitted by the Author:	22-May-2020
Complete List of Authors:	Forjanés, Pablo; Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Mineralogía y Petrología Gómez-Barreiro, Juan; Universidad de Salamanca, Departamento de Geología Morales, Juan; Universidad de Salamanca, Departamento de Geología Manuel Astilleros, Jose; Complutense University of Madrid, Mineralogía y Petrología; Instituto de Geociencias, UCM, CSIC Fernandez-Diaz, Lourdes; Complutense University of Madrid, Mineralogía y Petrología; Instituto de Geociencias, UCM, CSIC

Epitactic growth of celestite on anhydrite: Substrate induced twinning and morphological evolution of aggregates.

Pablo Forjanes^{1*}, Juan Gómez Barreiro², Juan Morales², José Manuel Astilleros^{1,3} and Lurdes Fernández-Díaz^{1,3}.

1. Departamento de Mineralogía y Petrología. Universidad Complutense de Madrid. 28040. Madrid, Spain.
2. Departamento de Geología, Universidad de Salamanca. 37008. Salamanca, Spain.
3. Instituto de Geociencias (IGEO), (UCM, CSIC). 28040. Madrid, Spain.

*corresponding author: pforjane@ucm.es

Abstract

Epitactic crystal growth plays a main role in the development of mineral processes and in the synthesis of advanced materials. Celestite (SrSO_4) forms epitactic overgrowths on anhydrite (CaSO_4) (100), (010) and (001) surfaces interacting with Sr-bearing aqueous solutions. Two populations of differently oriented celestite crystals related by symmetry operators of substrate are identified on $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ and $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ anhydrite substrates by SEM observations and synchrotron X-ray diffraction analysis. Substrate-induced twins arise after the coalescence of individuals belonging to these populations. Progressing growth results in a marked morphological evolution of epitactic celestite, whose crystals undergo sustained branching and loss of co-orientation that result in the formation of sheaf-like aggregates, on $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$, and swan-like aggregates, on $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$. We relate this evolution to celestite growth in a Ca-rich environment due to continued anhydrite dissolution and incorporation of small amounts of Ca into celestite structure. This incorporation would induce lattice strain which would be released through the formation of dislocations. The regular arrangement of these dislocations in small-angle

24 boundaries would result in progressive splitting, driving the evolution from celestite single
25 crystals to aggregates. Sharp compositional gradients in the boundary layer could explain the
26 anisotropic development that leads to the formation of the swan-like celestites.

27 ***Introduction***

28
29 Epitactic growth is a main step in the synthesis of materials for industrial applications, from
30 electronics to semiconductors.^{1,2} In geological environments, epitactic growth also plays a
31 relevant role, facilitating the development of mineral transformations between phases that
32 share structural elements.³⁻⁹ Epitactic growth can proceed through different mechanisms which
33 are mainly determined by the goodness of the structural matching between the overgrowth and
34 the substrate phase through their interface.¹⁰ Furthermore, the quality of the structural fitting
35 defines the degree of substrate-overgrowth interface coherency and adhesion.¹⁰ Epitactic
36 growth that involves low interface misfits is commonly characterized by coherent interfaces and
37 high substrate-overgrowth adhesions and occurs through the Frank-Van der Merwe
38 mechanism.^{11,12} In contrast, higher interface misfits lead to epitactic growth dominated by the
39 Stranski-Krastanov or the Volmer-Weber mechanisms, resulting in the formation of epitactic
40 layers with poor substrate-overgrowth adhesion and semi to incoherent interfaces.^{1,10,13-18} Even
41 when there exists a good fitting between the substrate and the overgrowth, coherent or semi
42 coherent interfaces are associated to the development of a certain degree of lattice-mismatch
43 strain in the overgrowth, which progressively accumulates as the epitactic growth progresses
44 and the thickness of the overgrowth increases.¹⁹ Lattice-mismatch strain can eventually be
45 relaxed through the formation of dislocations.^{20,21} Indeed, nucleation of strain dislocations is a
46 common phenomenon observed, for example, during the preparation of heteroepitaxial
47 semiconductor films.²²⁻²⁴ Strain dislocations represent an intrinsic source of misorientation,
48 whose development leads to the progressive loss of coherency. There also exist extrinsic factors

49 that can induce a progressive loss of co-alignment within an epitactic layer. One of these factors
50 is the presence of impurities in the growth medium. The incorporation of these impurities into
51 the structure of the overgrowth induces lattice strain and eventually can lead to the nucleation
52 of dislocations, polygonization and split growth phenomena.^{18, 25,26}

53 Celestite is the main ore of strontium.²⁷ All large exploitable deposits of celestite are associated
54 to sedimentary rocks, where their formation is thought to be related to the interaction of
55 calcium sulphate minerals, namely gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) and/or (CaSO_4) anhydrite, with Sr-rich
56 fluids.²⁸ Here, we study the formation of celestite (SrSO_4) on the three main cleavage surfaces
57 of anhydrite, (100), (010) and (001), upon their interaction with Sr-bearing aqueous solutions.
58 Celestite initially grows oriented on all anhydrite cleavage surfaces. However, a progressive loss
59 of co-orientation is observed as celestite growth progresses. We describe the epitactic
60 relationships between celestite and anhydrite substrates as well as the evolution of celestite
61 crystal morphology and the associated progressive loss of co-orientation during growth. By
62 combining morphological observations and crystallographic and chemical analyses we aim to
63 advance in the understanding of the factors that control the evolution of epitactic growth in
64 natural multicomponent systems.

65 ***Experimental***

66 We conducted interaction experiments between anhydrite (CaSO_4) surfaces and Sr-bearing
67 aqueous solutions ($[\text{Sr}]_{\text{aq}} = 0.1, 1.0, 10$ and 50 g/L) at $25^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and atmospheric pressure.
68 The Sr-bearing aqueous solutions were prepared by dissolving reagent-grade $\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in high
69 purity deionized water (MiliQ) (18 M Ω cm). The anhydrite samples were 1 mm thick, square-
70 shaped (3×3 mm²) slices of highly pure blue single crystals from Naica (Chihuahua, México).
71 These slices were cut parallel to the (001), (010) and (100) planes. Their orientation with respect

72 to the main crystallographic directions of anhydrite was confirmed by observing their
73 interference figure using a polarized optical microscope.

74 Freshly cleaved anhydrite slices were placed in glass reactors, laying on one of their squared
75 surfaces. The reactors were then filled with 5-ml of the Sr-bearing aqueous solution and sealed
76 with a polystyrene cap. The experiments were finished after set interaction times (30 minutes;
77 1, 2 and 6 hours; 1, 5, 7, 14 and 20 days). Independent runs were conducted for each of the
78 three cleavage surfaces and each time of interaction considered. After finishing the
79 experiments, the anhydrite samples were removed from the Sr-bearing solutions, thoroughly
80 rinsed with MiliQ water and left to dry overnight at 45°C in a thermostatic chamber. Afterwards,
81 anhydrite samples were mounted on holders, with their larger surface that had been exposed
82 to the Sr-bearing solution lying upwards. New phases formed on anhydrite surfaces were
83 analyzed by glancing incidence X-ray diffraction (GIXRD) using a Philips X'Pert PRO MRD
84 diffractometer equipped with a Cu-K α source (45 kV, 40 mA), a X-ray parabolic mirror in the
85 incident beam and a parallel plate collimator with flat graphite monochromator in the diffracted
86 beam (Xe proportional detector). The surfaces were scanned over the range $2\theta = 20-90^\circ$ at a
87 scan speed of $0.8^\circ/\text{min}$ and with a 0.1° beam incidence angle. Standard mineral files of the
88 Crystallographic Open Database (COD, 2017 version) and diffraction diagrams were correlated
89 to determine solid phases. Anhydrite samples were then coated, first with carbon and then with
90 gold, and studied by means of a scanning electron microscope (JEOL JSM 6400, 40 kV) equipped
91 with an energy dispersive spectrometer (LINK Ex1; Oxford Instruments 80 mm² X-Max SDD) to
92 obtain information on both, dissolution features and chemical and morphological characteristics
93 of precipitates newly formed on anhydrite surfaces as a result of its interaction with the Sr-
94 bearing aqueous solutions. Cross sections of some of the anhydrite samples were also prepared
95 by embedding them in epoxy resin and polishing down to the middle of the crystals.
96 Backscattered scanning electron microscope (BSEM) imaging of these cross-sections allowed for
97 the identification of different phases on the basis of their difference in contrast. The shape of

98 the newly formed crystals was modelled using the JCrystal software (KrystalShaper, 2019).
 99 Finally, structure computer models were constructed using the CrystalMaker software for
 100 analysing the crystallographic relationships between anhydrite surfaces and the newly formed
 101 precipitates.²⁹

102 Synchrotron diffraction experiments

103 Cleaved slices of anhydrite were prepared as described in the previous section to explore the
 104 epitactic growth of celestite on (100), (010) and (001) anhydrite substrates through synchrotron
 105 diffraction experiments. After the interaction with the Sr-bearing solutions, the samples were
 106 mounted on a goniometer with a glass pin for rotation. The experimental reference system is
 107 shown in Figure 1, where the rotation axis ($\omega // Y$) is parallel to anhydrite [001], [100] and [100]
 108 for (100), (010) and (001) anhydrite slices, respectively. The diffraction experiments were done
 109 at the ID11 beamline at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF), France.³⁰ The
 110 experimental setup and procedure were as follows. A monochromatic X-rays beam (dimensions
 111 0.5 x 0.5 mm; wavelength 0.030996 nm) was directed at the sample, previously mounted on a
 112 goniometer head and investigated in transmission geometry. Diffraction images were recorded
 113 by a FreLoN detector (2048 x 2048 pixels), 23 cm away from the sample.

114

115 **Figure 1:** Experimental (A) and sample (B) reference system. Coordinate system for anhydrite (100) sample is described
116 in (B) as an example. For anhydrite (001) and (010), $Y//[100]_{Anh} - X//[010]_{Anh}$ and $Y//[100]_{Anh} - X//[001]_{Anh}$,
117 respectively. See the text for a discussion.

118 Diffraction images display both many celestite Debye rings with azimuthal intensity variations
119 indicating texture, and very bright anhydrite single crystal diffraction spots (Figure 2). During
120 data collection, in order to prevent the detector saturation, 60 images were collected with a
121 short acquisition time (0.5 s) for each sample. In order to improve pole figure coverage, the
122 sample slice was rotated around an axis perpendicular to the beam ($\omega // Y$; Figure 1) from +10°
123 to -10°. A CeO₂ standard was measured to determine instrumental parameters, like sample to
124 detector distance.

125 Diffraction images from each rotation were corrected for FReLon geometrical distortion and
126 merged into a single image in TIFF format, using Fit2D software.³¹ Images were decomposed
127 with the Rietveld program MAUD (Material Analysis Using Diffraction)³² into 72 azimuthal
128 sectors of 5°, over which intensity was integrated, providing a total of 216 diffraction spectra
129 per sample (Figure 2). In some cases, the severe overlapping of the anhydrite single crystal
130 pattern prevented the use of some sectors, which were manually eliminated from the dataset.
131 In the Rietveld refinement, the celestite crystal structure by Hawthorne and Ferguson³³ (*Pnma*;
132 $a = 8.360 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 5.352 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.858 \text{ \AA}$) was used as reference.

133 For quantitative texture analysis, E-WIMV algorithm³⁴ was applied, as implemented in MAUD,
134 without imposing any sample symmetry. The final celestite orientation distributions (OD) were
135 exported to BEARTEX for additional processing and recalculation of pole figures.³⁵ Texture
136 strength is quantified in pole-figures density scale (multiples of a random distribution, m.r.d.)
137 and F² index.³⁶ A detailed description of the method is published elsewhere.³⁷⁻³⁹

138

139

140

141

142

143

Figure 2: Diffraction Images with Debye rings (celestite) and spots (anhydrite), for the three different substrate orientations studied: (a) anhydrite (001), (b) anhydrite (010) and (c) anhydrite (100). Intensity variations along Debye rings are due to celestite texture. Some planes are indexed. Reference system (XYZ) as defined in Figure 1.

144

Results

145

146

147

148

149

150

151

SEM imaging of freshly cleaved anhydrite (001), (010) and (100) surfaces shows that they consist of large flat terraces bounded by macrosteps. Slightly different features are observed on the (001) surface, which appears rougher and contains a larger number of steps than the other two surfaces. In all cases, after 30 minutes of interaction between the anhydrite substrate and the Sr-bearing solution, the formation of etch-pits on flat terraces is observed (Figure 3a). The progress of the interaction latter leads to the nucleation of a secondary phase regardless of the anhydrite surface considered (Figure 3b).

152

153

154

155

156

157

158

Figure 3c shows a typical EDX spectrum from one of these newly formed crystals, which shows that they primarily consist of oxygen, sulfur and strontium, with small contents of calcium (up to 1.5 wt. %). EDX analyses support that these crystals are Ca-bearing celestite (Figure 3c). This interpretation is further supported by the results of GIXRD analysis. A typical GIXRD diagram of these crystals is shown in Figure 3d. All diffraction peaks match those of celestite, although they appear slightly shifted towards higher 2θ angles compared to their positions in the standard XRD pattern of celestite (COD 96-900-4484).

159

160

161 **Figure 3.** (a) SEM image of an anhydrite (100) cleavage surface after interaction with pure water. Anhydrite surfaces
 162 are characterized by the presence of flat terraces and large macrosteps. Once the dissolution of anhydrite starts, etch
 163 pits develop on the terraces. The orientation and geometry of these pits allows us to identify main crystallographic
 164 directions on the substrate. (b) The interaction of the anhydrite surfaces with a Sr-bearing aqueous solution leads to
 165 the formation of celestite single crystals, with a habit defined by a combination of the {001} pinacoid and the {210}
 166 and {101} rhombic prisms (see the drawing). (c) EDX analyses confirmed that the newly formed celestite contains a
 167 small amount of Ca. (d) Glancing incidence X-ray diffraction pattern (0.1°) recorded after 2 hours of interaction
 168 between an anhydrite (001) surface and a strontium-bearing aqueous solution. Main diffraction peaks in the GIXRD
 169 pattern match well those of celestite, although they appear slightly shifted towards higher values of 2θ.

170 The substrate surface area carpeted by celestite crystals progressively increases and celestite
 171 crystal growth and coalescence leads to the formation of a continuous layer on the anhydrite
 172 substrate. The thickness of this celestite layer progressively increases through the inward
 173 displacement of the celestite-anhydrite interface. The kinetics of the anhydrite by celestite

174 transformation depends on the orientation of the anhydrite substrate. A continuous layer of
 175 celestite carpets the (001) anhydrite substrate after one day of interaction, while the formation
 176 of a celestite continuous layer on (100) and (010) requires three days (Figure 4a).

177 Overgrown celestite initially appears as micrometer-sized single crystals that grow oriented on
 178 all anhydrite surfaces studied (Figure 4b). Celestite crystal habit is mainly defined by flat faces
 179 belonging to the {001} pinacoid and the {210} prism. Though less developed, some crystals also
 180 show faces that belong to the {101} prism (Figure 3b). Some differences are observed between
 181 the habits of celestite crystals that grow on different anhydrite surfaces. Furthermore, celestite
 182 crystals undergo significant morphological changes during growth. Epitactic relationships
 183 between celestite and each anhydrite substrate as well as substrate-specific celestite
 184 morphological features and their evolution are described in the following sections.

185
 186 **Figure 4.** (a) BSE image of an anhydrite crystal cross-cut along (100) after 7 days interaction with a Sr-bearing aqueous
 187 solution. The different thickness of the replaced-by-celestite layer reflects the different reactivity of the (001)_{Anh} and
 188 (010)_{Anh} surfaces. (b) Celestite secondary crystals growing clearly oriented on an anhydrite (001) substrate.

189 190 **Celestite overgrowth on anhydrite (100)**

191 Crystallographic directions on anhydrite (100) surfaces are identified based on its dissolution
 192 features, which mainly consist in shallow, pencil-shaped etch-pits elongated along [001].⁴⁰

193 Celestite crystals that form on anhydrite (100) surfaces upon interaction with Sr-bearing
194 aqueous solutions preferentially nucleate on edges of these etch pits or in nearby areas. The
195 habit of these crystals is defined by faces that belong to the {001} pinacoid and, to a lesser
196 extent, to the {210} and {101} prisms.

197 Celestite secondary crystals grow oriented with respect to the anhydrite substrate with their

198 {001} pinacoid parallel to the anhydrite (100) substrate (Figure 5a). Two populations can be

199 distinguished among these oriented celestite crystals. One population includes numerous

200 individuals and consists of crystals that grow with their $\langle 120 \rangle$ edges parallel to anhydrite $[010]$

201 direction (Figure 5b; yellow star). The other population comprises fewer celestite crystals, and

202 these are oriented with their $\langle 120 \rangle$ edges parallel to $[001]$ direction in the anhydrite substrate
 203 (Figure 5b; red star). The local coalescence of celestite crystals belonging to each of these

204 populations leads to the formation of simple twins (Figure 5b and 5c). Furthermore, the
 205 coalescence of celestite crystals of the same population but with different orientation due to
 206 existence of symmetry operators (mirror planes and 2-fold axis) inherent to the anhydrite
 207 structure and normal to the anhydrite (100) surface can also lead to the formation simple twins
 208 (Figure 5b). As interaction between anhydrite (100) surface and Sr-bearing solutions progresses
 209 and celestite crystals continue to grow, they develop disoriented subunits, whose number
 210 increases along time and is accompanied by a progressive loss of parallelism between celestite
 211 and anhydrite directions. As can be seen in Figure 5d, the development of subunits in celestite
 212 crystals growing epitaxially on anhydrite (100) involves two combined misorientational spreads.
 213 One spread is associated to a progressive loss of parallelism between $(001)_{Cit}$ and $(100)_{Anh}$, while
 214 the other comprises a gradual loss of parallelism between $[120]_{Cit}$ and both $[010]_{Anh}$ and $[001]_{Anh}$.
 215 Maximum orientational spreads reach 20° after 5 days interaction.

216

217 **Figure 5.** (a) Celestite crystals grow oriented on anhydrite (100) surfaces. (b) The interaction of anhydrite (100)
218 surfaces with a Sr-bearing aqueous solution promotes the formation of etch pits that run parallel to [001] and the
219 epitaxial nucleation of secondary celestite crystals. The epitaxy between anhydrite and celestite involves the matching
220 of the plane (100) of anhydrite with the plane (001) of celestite. Celestite <120> edges are parallel to the [010] direction
221 in the anhydrite substrate (yellow star) and, to a lesser extent, to the [001] direction in the anhydrite substrate (red
222 star). (c) The coalescence of two neighbored celestite crystals with different epitaxial orientations leads to the
223 formation of simple twins. (b) Celestite crystals develop progressively misoriented subunits as their growth
224 progresses.

225 **Celestite overgrowth on anhydrite (001)**

226 Etch pits formed on anhydrite (001) surface in contact with Sr-bearing aqueous solutions are
227 elongated along [100] and bounded by steps parallel to [100] and [010].⁴⁰ The coalescence of
228 this oriented etch pits results in the formation of evenly spaced grooves that run along [100].
229 These grooves are deep and give anhydrite (001) surface a very rough appearance. Celestite
230 crystals nucleate on the edges of these grooves soon after the beginning of anhydrite interaction
231 with the Sr-bearing aqueous solution. On anhydrite (001), celestite crystals show a rhombus-like
232 habit, dominated by faces corresponding to the {001} pinacoid and the {210} prism (Figure 4b
233 and 6a). These crystals grow with one face of their {210} prisms laying in direct contact with the
234 anhydrite (001) substrate, $(001)_{\text{Anh}} \parallel (210)_{\text{Cit}}$, and their larger faces, those corresponding to the
235 {001} pinacoid, oriented perpendicular to both, the anhydrite substrate and the deep grooves
236 on it, so that $\{001\}_{\text{Cit}} \perp (001)_{\text{Anh}}$ and $[100]_{\text{Anh}}$ (Figure 6). As a result, celestite [120] edges (defined
237 by the intersection of {210} and {001} forms) appear oriented parallel to $[010]_{\text{Anh}}$, while [001]
238 edges (defined by the intersection of faces corresponding to the {210} form) are oriented parallel
239 to $[100]_{\text{Anh}}$ (Figure 6b and 6c). Two approximately equally abundant orientations of celestite
240 crystals can be distinguished (Figure 6a). These two orientations are related by a mirror plane
241 symmetry operator parallel to anhydrite [100] direction, this is, the direction of the grooves on
242 the anhydrite (001) substrate (Figure 6c). Additionally, another much less abundant population

243 of celestite crystals oriented with their [120] edges parallel to $[100]_{\text{Anh}}$ is also observed (Figure
244 4b; white arrow).

245 Similarly to the observed on anhydrite (100) substrate, epitactic celestite crystals that grow on
246 an anhydrite (001) substrate progressively develop increasingly misoriented subunits and evolve
247 from single crystals to crystal aggregates. This evolution is significantly more marked in the
248 region of the celestite crystal that directly lays in contact with the anhydrite (001) substrate
249 (Figure 6a). In this region (marked with a red ellipse in Figure 6b) subunits develop due to the
250 combination of two different misorientational spreads. One spread involves the progressive loss
251 of parallelism between $(001)_{\text{Cit}}$ and $[010]_{\text{Anh}}$ while the celestite plane remains perpendicular to
252 $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$. The other spread arises from the progressive tilting in the orientation of $(001)_{\text{Cit}}$, which
253 evolves from perpendicular to parallel to $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$. The combination of both misorientational
254 spreads gives a swan like-shape to these crystals, where the misorientational spread between
255 subunits can reach up to 180° (Figure 6a). In contrast, orientational spread in the region of the
256 celestite crystal that does not directly lays in contact with the anhydrite (001) substrate (marked
257 with a yellow ellipse in Figure 6b) exclusively arises from the change in the orientation of $(001)_{\text{Cit}}$,
258 which despite progressively losing its parallelism to $[010]_{\text{Anh}}$ remains perpendicular to $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$.
259 In this case, the maximum misorientation between crystal subunits only reaches up to 45° . The
260 peculiar swan like morphology of celestite crystal aggregates resulting from the development of
261 the described misorientational spreads is depicted in Figure 6, where a simulation of a typical
262 celestite crystal growing on anhydrite (001) surface as a result of the interaction of the later with
263 a Sr-bearing aqueous solution has been included (Figure 6d).

264

265 **Figure 6.** SEM images showing celestite crystals that grow on anhydrite (001) surfaces. (a,b) Celestite crystals grow
 266 oriented so that $(001)_{\text{Anh}} \parallel (210)_{\text{Clt}}$. The epitaxy between both phases involves the matching of the plane (001) of
 267 anhydrite with the plane (210) of celestite. Celestite $\langle 120 \rangle$ edges run parallel to $[010]$ direction in the anhydrite
 268 substrate. The existence of a mirror plane perpendicular to anhydrite (001) substrate generates two populations of
 269 celestite crystals. (c) Celestite single crystals progressively develop subunits during growth. These subunits are
 270 arranged according to two orientational spreads. Wider orientational spread occurs in the region of the celestite
 271 crystal that is closer to the substrate, which leads to the development of a swan-like habit. (d). Simulation of a typical
 272 celestite crystal growing on an anhydrite (001) cleavage surface.

273 **Celestite overgrowth on anhydrite (010)**

274 Etch pits formed on anhydrite (010) surface upon dissolution in contact with Sr-bearing aqueous
 275 solutions are shallow and rectangular-shaped (Figure 7). These pits appear elongated along
 276 $[001]$ and bounded by steps parallel to $[100]$ and $[001]$. A small population of platy and rhombus-
 277 shaped celestite crystals whose habit is dominated by the $\{001\}$ pinacoid also forms on anhydrite
 278 (010) substrates. All these crystals grow on either cleavage macrosteps or steps bounding etch

279 pits. Both the absence of celestite crystals growing on terraces and the much smaller celestite
 280 crystal density on this substrate compared to that observed on anhydrite (100) and (001)
 281 surfaces points to celestite nucleation actually taking place on the two latter surfaces where
 282 these two planes are exposed on steps rather than directly on anhydrite (010). SEM observations
 283 suggest that celestite crystals that grow on anhydrite (010) substrates also develop a certain
 284 degree of misorientational spread that leads to the formation of subunits. However, the
 285 characteristics of this misorientational spread are much more difficult to evaluate due to the
 286 smaller number and size of celestite crystals that grow on this anhydrite substrate together to
 287 their unclear epitaxial relationships with respect to the anhydrite (010) substrate.

288
 289 **Figure 7.** The interaction of anhydrite (010) surfaces with Sr-bearing aqueous solutions promotes the formation of
 290 celestite crystals poorly oriented with respect to the anhydrite substrate.

291 Texture analysis

292 The Rietveld processing results in a good data fit (Figure 8), which ensures a convergence of the
 293 refined parameters. Recalculated celestite 001, 100, 110, 101, 210 and 120 pole figures for each
 294 anhydrite orientation ((100)_{Anh}, (001)_{Anh} and (010)_{Anh}) are shown in Figure 9.

295 **Figure 8.** a) Total profile obtained by integrating 216 spectra from 0° to 360° azimuth. Experimental data are shown
296 as dots and the line is the Rietveld fit. Some planes are indexed. b) 'Unrolled' diffraction image showing intensity
297 variations due to texture. The Rietveld fit on top reproduce well the measured diffraction data below.

298 In all the samples, celestite preferred orientation with different geometrical relationships to the
299 anhydrite substrate is observed. Celestite overgrowths on (100)_{Anh} show the strongest texture,
300 with most of the celestite crystals showing preferred orientation (pole figure minimum = 0.1
301 m.r.d. Figure 9a). In contrast, on (001)_{Anh} and (010)_{Anh}, although most crystals are preferentially
302 oriented, there is a significant proportion of them that appear randomly oriented, with minima
303 ranging from 0.48 to 0.39 m.r.d. (Figures 9c to 9f).

304 Overall, most of celestite crystals fit into two textural components (A and B; Figure 9), which can
305 directly be correlated with the SEM overgrowth patterns described in the previous section.

306

307

308

309

310

311

Figure 9. Pole figures of celestite crystals growing on the three anhydrite substrates considered: a) $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ b) $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ and c) $(010)_{\text{Anh}}$. On the left column, main textural components: $(001)_{\text{Clt}}$ and $(210)_{\text{Clt}}$ (A: grey; B: black) are summarized in stereographic projection. Dashed circles represent different angles to the anhydrite substrate. Main epitactic relationships are illustrated with simple schemes on each case (see Figures 10 and 11). The absence of oriented celestite overgrowth on $(010)_{\text{Anh}}$ suggests that texture in this surface arises from mixing crystals growing on $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$

312 and $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ steps and/or edge pits exposed in this surface (Figure 7). The reference system XYZ has been defined in
313 Figure 1 and indicates the orientation of anhydrite directions ($[100]$, $[010]$ and $[001]$) for each plane. Equal angle
314 projections are marked with linear contour intervals (m.r.d.: multiples of a random distribution).

315 **Celestite texture on anhydrite (100)**

316 Celestite texture on anhydrite (100) has the strongest preferred orientation, with an $F^2= 6.1087$
317 and a pole figure max/min= 3.97/0.1 m.r.d. (Figure 9a). Two textural components are identified.
318 Component A is defined by celestite crystals with their (001) poles distributed in two maxima
319 around anhydrite $[100]$ ($//Z$ axis) and elongated preferably along the X-axis ($// [010]_{\text{Anh}}$). The
320 angular dispersion around the Z-axis is about 50° . Furthermore, celestite (210) poles show two
321 peripheral maxima parallel to the X- and Y-axes, separated $70\text{-}80^\circ$. A similar pattern is observed
322 for $(120)_{\text{Clt}}$ poles.

323 In the textural component B, celestite (001) poles show an elongated maximum parallel to the
324 Y-axis, with an angular dispersion of 35° in the YZ plane and 25° in the XY plane. Celestite (210)
325 poles define a small maximum and an incomplete girdle between X and Y axes at 30° and 50-
326 60° , respectively, from Z-axis.

327 **Celestite texture on anhydrite (001)**

328 Texture strength of celestite on this plane is $F^2= 2.3363$, and pole figure max./min.= 1.92/0.48
329 m.r.d (Figure 9c). Overall, there is a significant number of celestite crystals randomly oriented
330 (0.48 m.r.d.). Textural component A includes numerous celestite crystals with their (210) poles
331 parallel to $[001]_{\text{Anh}}$ ($//Z$ axis) and an angular dispersion (ca. 15°) about anhydrite $[001]$. A second
332 (210) point maximum is identified in the X-axis at 76° . The $(120)_{\text{Clt}}$ and $(100)_{\text{Clt}}$ poles are also
333 concentrated in the surroundings of the Z-axis ($//[001]_{\text{Anh}}$) ($\pm 20^\circ$). The peripheral distribution
334 of the $(001)_{\text{Clt}}$ poles around $[100]_{\text{Anh}}$ ($\pm 30^\circ$) is consistent with textural component A.

335 Celestite crystals in component B depict a stronger texture, with $(001)_{\text{Cit}} // (001)_{\text{Anh}}$ ($\pm 20\text{-}30^\circ$,
336 maximum dispersion 56° along X and Y-axes). A set of $(210)_{\text{Cit}}$ poles concentrate between 16 and
337 30° from $[100]_{\text{Anh}}$ along the Y-axis. A projection of $(210)_{\text{Cit}}$ along X-axis is geometrically consistent
338 and partially overlaps with A-component, what prevents a detailed distinction. Moreover,
339 $(100)_{\text{Cit}}$ peripheral girdle and a point maximum close to $[100]_{\text{Anh}}$ ($\pm 20^\circ$) are a coherent part of
340 the B-component.

341 **Celestite texture on anhydrite (010)**

342 SEM observations showed no oriented celestite overgrowths on $(010)_{\text{Anh}}$ (Figure 7). Texture
343 analysis, however, shows distinct pole patterns (Figure 9e and 9f) and a considerable strength
344 ($F^2 = 6.1055$), with pole figure maximum and minimum of 2.77 and 0.39 m.r.d. Most celestite
345 crystals have their (001) poles parallel to the X axis ($// [001]_{\text{Anh}}$) with an angular dispersion of
346 $\pm 75^\circ$ in the XY plane, and $\pm 30^\circ$ in the XZ plane of the reference system (Figure 1). The $(001)_{\text{Cit}}$
347 poles depict two secondary point maxima, which fall along Y-axis, representing $(001)_{\text{Cit}}$ planes at
348 $\pm 50^\circ$ to the $(010)_{\text{Anh}}$ substrate. $(210)_{\text{Cit}}$ poles show a peripheral distribution close to the X-axis
349 and between X- and Y-axes. Other point maxima of $(210)_{\text{Cit}}$ poles fall close to the Y-axis, forming
350 an angle of 40° and 60° with the substrate. Geometrical constraints suggest that celestite texture
351 is compatible with a mixture of two populations developed on step and pit edges, where
352 $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ and $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ surfaces are exposed (inset; Figure 9e).

353 **Discussion**

354 We observe that the interaction of Sr-bearing aqueous solutions with any of the three main
355 anhydrite cleavage surfaces leads to the precipitation of celestite crystals that grow oriented
356 with respect to the substrate. This precipitation is the direct consequence of the dissolution of
357 the anhydrite substrate and the concomitant release of both SO_4^{2-} and Ca^{2+} ions to the aqueous
358 solutions, which rapidly becomes supersaturated with respect to celestite. As soon as the

359 supersaturation threshold for celestite heterogeneous nucleation is overcome, celestite crystals
 360 form on anhydrite substrates. The nucleation and growth of these crystals removes SO_4^{2-} ions,
 361 as well as Sr^{2+} , from the solution and promotes further dissolution of the anhydrite substrate,
 362 which in turn results in the solution again becoming supersaturated with respect to celestite,
 363 facilitating celestite crystals to growth. In this way, a dissolution-crystallization feedback loop is
 364 established, which operates as long as the system does not become exhausted of either anhydrite
 365 and/or dissolved Sr or the celestite does not completely armor the anhydrite substrate from
 366 interaction with the solution. This loop operates according to the following reactions:

369 As stated above, we observe the formation of significantly higher density of celestite crystals on
 370 $(001)_{Anh}$ than on $(100)_{Anh}$ and $(010)_{Anh}$. This higher crystal density can be explained if we take into
 371 account the dissolution kinetics of the three anhydrite substrates. *In situ* Atomic Force
 372 Microscopy experiments conducted by Shindo et al⁴⁰ evidenced that the dissolution of $(001)_{Anh}$
 373 in contact with water takes place at a much faster rate than the dissolution of $(100)_{Anh}$ and
 374 $(010)_{Anh}$. It stands to reason that $(001)_{Anh}$ will also dissolve at a much faster rate in contact with
 375 a Sr-bearing aqueous solution, which will result in a solution in contact with $(001)_{Anh}$ becoming
 376 supersaturated with respect to celestite earlier than a solution in contact with $(100)_{Anh}$ and
 377 $(010)_{Anh}$. Assuming that anhydrite dissolution is the rate limiting step in the dissolution-
 378 crystallization reaction, the faster dissolution of $(001)_{Anh}$ will result in the dissolution-
 379 crystallization loop also operating at a faster rate when the Sr-bearing solution interacts with
 380 this substrate.

381 Regardless of the anhydrite surface considered, celestite crystals show habits dominated by the
 382 $\{001\}$ pinacoid, combined with the $\{210\}$ and $\{101\}$ prisms, which appear less developed. All

383 these forms are common in natural celestite crystals.⁴¹ Moreover, they define the theoretical
384 habit of celestite, according to the Periodic Bond Chain (PBC) analysis conducted by Hartman
385 and Strom⁴² for crystals with the barite structure. This analysis attributes the lowest attachment
386 energy to the {001} form, which explains that it is the most developed form in all the newly
387 formed celestite crystals, regardless of the anhydrite substrate on which they are growing.

388 **Epitactic Relationships between Anhydrite and Celestite**

389 The structural matching between the overgrowth and the substrate is a key parameter that must
390 be considered in order to understand the development of an epitaxy. A good matching between
391 layers of two different phases requires that their structures share both, geometrical features
392 and structural elements. Despite crystallizing in different systems, anhydrite (space group
393 *Amma*, $a = 6.993 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 6.995 \text{ \AA}$, and $c = 6.245 \text{ \AA}$) and celestite (space group *Pnma*, $a = 8.360 \text{ \AA}$,
394 $b = 5.352 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.858 \text{ \AA}$), it does exist a clear affinity between the structures of these phases.
395 Indeed, both structures are orthorhombic and consist of sulfate – cation chains linked into
396 sheets which in turn are linked together to build up a framework. As a result, the formation of
397 (001) and (210) layers of celestite onto the (100) and (001) surfaces of anhydrite does not result
398 in the interruption of the sulfate – cation sequences but guarantees their continuity, thereby
399 also ensuring the structural continuity between the two phases involved in the epitaxy. This
400 structural continuity through the interphase constitutes a basic requirement condition for the
401 existence of epitactic relationships between two crystalline individuals.⁴³ On the other hand, in
402 all the epitactic relationships described above between the celestite and the three anhydrite
403 substrates considered, the matching between the structure of these two phases involves
404 crystallographic directions that are parallel to PBCs: In the structure of anhydrite three PBCs run
405 parallel to its main crystallographic axes, whereas in the structure of celestite the most stable
406 PBCs run parallel to [001] and $\langle 120 \rangle$. According to the PBC theory,¹⁰ this scenario favors the

407 development of an epitaxy since a minimum interface energy is achieved when there is a
 408 coincidence between close-packed atomic rows (defined by the PBCs).

409 Beyond structural considerations, the formation of an epitaxy also requires low misfit values
 410 between the lattice planes involved. Lattice misfit (*mf*) can be expressed by means of the
 411 equation (van der Merwe, 1978):

$$412 \quad mf(\%) = \frac{t_{[uvw]_{\text{Cls}}} - t_{[uvw]_{\text{Anh}}}}{t_{[uvw]_{\text{Anh}}}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

413 where $t_{[uvw]}$ is the repeating period (distance between successive equivalent SO_4 groups) along
 414 the $[uvw]$ direction of the substrate (anhydrite) and overgrowth (celestite). Negative misfit
 415 values mean that the unit cell of the overgrowth is contracted along $[uvw]$ in comparison to the
 416 unit cell of the substrate ($t_{[uvw]_{\text{Cls}}} < t_{[uvw]_{\text{Anh}}}$). Similar repeating periods ($mf \leq |10|\%$ to $|12|\%$)
 417 mean a good matching between the two structures and favour the formation of an epitaxy.^{10,44}
 418 Table 1 shows the misfits calculated for the shared directions between celestite and anhydrite
 419 defined in the epitaxy. In all the cases, $mf \leq |10|\%$, which puts them within the acceptable limits
 420 for the formation of an orientated overgrowth of celestite on the substrate of anhydrite. The
 421 matching between the two structures through the $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ and $(210)_{\text{Clt}}$ is remarkably good, with
 422 linear misfits that are lower than $|3|\%$ for all the shared directions involved in the epitaxy.
 423 Moreover, the fact that *a* and *b* axes in anhydrite are almost identical in length ($b-a = 0.002 \text{ \AA}$)
 424 explains the existence of two different populations of celestite, whose orientations are related
 425 by a pseudo 4-fold axis. Additionally, the less good matching between $[001]_{\text{Anh}}$ and $[120]_{\text{Clt}}$
 426 (8.74%) through anhydrite (100) surfaces explains that the population of celestite crystals that
 427 show this orientation is much less numerous than the one formed by celestite crystals oriented
 428 so that $[120]_{\text{Clt}}$ and $[010]_{\text{Anh}}$ are parallel, since a much better matching (-2.91%) exists between
 429 these two latter directions through anhydrite (100) surfaces (Figure 4b).

430 Table 1. Epitaxial relationships between anhydrite and celestite

Anhydrite (CaSO ₄)		Celestite (SrSO ₄)			Misfit (%)
Contact Plane	Parameter (Å)	Contact Plane	Parameter(Å)	Population	
(100)	2 x [010] = 13.990Å	(001)	[120] = 13.582 Å	1	-2.91
	2 x [001] = 12.490Å			2	8.74
(001)	2 x [010] = 13.990Å	(210)	[120] = 13.582Å	3	-2.91
	[100] = 6.993Å		[001] = 6.858Å		1.93
	2 x [100] = 13.986Å		[120] = 13.582Å	4	-2.88
	[010] = 6.995Å		[001] = 6.858Å		-1.96

431

432 As has been explained, on all the anhydrite surfaces studied several populations of differently
433 orientated celestite crystals are observed. For a given anhydrite substrate the orientations
434 shown by the celestite crystals that grow on it are related by symmetry operators which belong
435 to the symmetry class of anhydrite ($2/m\ 2/m\ 2/m$) and are perpendicular to that substrate. The
436 coalescence of differently oriented individuals as a result of their growth leads to the formation
437 of twins. "Substrate induced twinning" is a well-documented phenomenon which can lead to
438 the generation of specific textures.⁴⁴ The occurrence of substrate induced twinning has already
439 been reported associated to numerous dissolution-crystallization reactions that involve sulfate,
440 carbonate and/or phosphate mineral phases.^{14,17,45} One of these dissolution-crystallization
441 reactions involves the interaction of Pb-bearing aqueous solutions with anhydrite, which leads
442 to the precipitation of anglesite (PbSO₄) on anhydrite surfaces.¹⁷ Both, anglesite and celestite
443 belong to the barite group and, consequently, are isostructural. As reported by Morales et al¹⁷,
444 anglesite crystals also grow oriented on (100)_{Anh}, (010)_{Anh} and (001)_{Anh}, showing identical
445 epitaxial relationships with these substrates as described here for celestite.

446

447 The most striking difference between celestite and anglesite crystals growing on (100)_{Anh},
448 (010)_{Anh} and (001)_{Anh} regards the evolution of the characteristics of anglesite and celestite
449 crystals during growth. While anglesite crystals show no sign of branching and split growth and,
450 consequently, their orientation with respect to a given anhydrite substrate remains the same as

451 they grow, celestite crystals progressively develop subunits as their growth progresses,
452 concomitantly losing their single crystal character and their epitactic orientation with respect to
453 the anhydrite substrate. We interpret the marked splitting that results in the evolution of
454 celestite crystals from single to crystal aggregates as probably driven by the incorporation of
455 small amounts of Ca into the structure of celestite substituting Sr. While no Ca incorporation
456 was detected in the case on anglesite, most likely due to the very large difference between the
457 radii of both cations, celestite growing on anhydrite has up to 1.5 wt. % Ca, as determined by
458 EDX analysis. Still, the ionic radii of Sr^{2+} and Ca^{2+} also are significantly different and Ca
459 incorporation in Sr positions is due to stress celestite structure. The formation of dislocations is
460 a common way for crystal structures to release lattice strain.⁴⁶ These dislocations can appear
461 spatially arranged at regular intervals, leading to the formation of small-angle boundaries.⁴⁶
462 Between dislocations the lattice will be coherently continuous across these boundaries. This
463 impurity incorporation-related splitting mechanisms explains, for example, the formation of
464 sheaf-like and spherulitic morphologies in Mg-calcites.^{47,48} Small-angle boundaries define
465 individual subunits in celestite aggregates. Thus, we conclude that the incorporation of Ca in the
466 celestite growth steps causes the formation of small-angle boundary and leads to the marked
467 splitting of the celestite crystals involved in the development of sheaf-like aggregates (Figure
468 5b) on the $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ surface and swan-like aggregates on the $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ surface (Figure 6). The
469 anisotropic features of the splitting that leads to the formation of the latter aggregates may be
470 related to the development of sharp Ca^{2+} and SO_4^{2-} concentration gradients at the anhydrite-
471 aqueous solution interface (boundary layer) as soon as the anhydrite substrate starts to dissolve.
472 The development of such compositional gradients at the mineral–aqueous solution interface
473 during dissolution-crystallization reactions has been experimentally confirmed in numerous
474 systems.⁴⁹⁻⁵¹ These compositional gradients necessarily result in supersaturation gradients.
475 Since coupled dissolution-precipitation reactions are kinetically faster than diffusion through the
476 bulk aqueous solution, the region of the celestite crystals that directly lays in contact with the

477 anhydrite (001) substrate grows under higher supersaturation conditions than regions further
478 away from the substrate. This higher supersaturation would facilitate the incorporation of
479 higher amounts of Ca, which in turn would explain the further development of misorientational
480 spreads in the region of the celestite crystals in direct contact with the anhydrite (001) substrate.

481

482 **Celestite texture and epitactic growth on anhydrite**

483 Quantitative texture analysis has shown distinct textural components of celestite crystals
484 growing on anhydrite faces. $(001)_{\text{Cit}}$ and $(210)_{\text{Cit}}$ pole figures are particularly relevant to correlate
485 texture and morphological features as observed under SEM. Two main textural components (A
486 and B, Figure 9) are clearly observed in $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ and $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ substrates. In contrast, celestite
487 texture on $(010)_{\text{Anh}}$ shows a more complex pattern, which we interpret as arising from the mixed
488 contribution of celestite crystals that nucleate oriented on steps and edge pits. On these edges,
489 $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ and $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ surfaces are exposed to the interaction with the Sr-bearing aqueous
490 solution. Thus, celestite texture on $(010)_{\text{Anh}}$ would be the result of celestite epitactic growth on
491 $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ and $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ rather than on the former surface. An explanative schematic of these
492 orientational relationships is depicted in the left column in Figure 9.

493 Celestite texture strength (F^2 -index) differs on each anhydrite face: $(100)_{\text{Anh}} > (001)_{\text{Anh}} > (010)_{\text{Anh}}$,
494 and pole figure density in $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ is about two times higher than in $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ face. Interestingly
495 most of celestite crystals on $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ are textured (pole figure minimum= 0.1 m.r.d.; Figure 9),
496 while a considerable number of celestite crystals on $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ are randomly distributed
497 (minimum= 0.48 m.r.d.).

498 Simple geometrical models have been elaborated to correlate celestite textural components and
499 direct observation under the scanning electron microscope of celestite crystals grown on
500 $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ (Figure 10) and $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ (Figure 11), respectively. In all cases pole figure orientation data
501 are evaluated within the coordinate system defined in Figure 1. As an example of the procedure,

502 a detailed stereographic projection of a $(001)_{\text{Ct}}$ plane inclined 60° to the substrate (i.e. $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$)
503 in the XYZ coordinate system is showed in Figure 10a. The location of the pole (P) is equivalent
504 to the one indicated in the real pole figure (Figure 10b). $(001)_{\text{Ct}}$ pole figure distribution depicts
505 a quasi-orthorhombic symmetry in which two rotations of $\pm 50^\circ$ and $\pm 30^\circ$ are identified in
506 the X- and Y-axis respectively (Figure 10b). Textural component A (Figure 9a) is compatible with
507 a rotation of $\pm 50^\circ$ around the Y-axis ($// [001]_{\text{Anh}}$) of celestite crystals initially oriented with
508 $(001)_{\text{Ct}} // (100)_{\text{Anh}}$ and $\langle 120 \rangle_{\text{Ct}} // [001]_{\text{Anh}}$ and $[010]_{\text{Anh}}$ (Figure 10c). Note that only one pair of
509 twinned celestite crystals is represented in Figure 10c for clarity, but substrate-induced twins
510 have 4-folds symmetry (Figures 5b, 5c and 10b). Crystal density is asymmetric along the X-axis,
511 suggesting that one twinned pair is much more abundant than the other (Figure 10b). This result
512 is in good agreement with our SEM observations and the epitaxy model proposed. The
513 component B could be conceived starting with celestite crystals originally oriented with $(001)_{\text{Ct}}$
514 $// Y$ -axis and $(210)_{\text{Ct}} // Z$ -axis (Figure 10d), then followed by a rotation of $\pm 30^\circ$ around the X-
515 axis ($// [001]_{\text{Anh}}$) (Figures 10b and 10d). This model is compatible with the orientation
516 distribution of the subunits constituting microscopic celestite aggregates (Figure 5d).

517

518

519 **Figure 10.** Conceptual models for celestite textural components developed on $(100)_{Anh}$ face (Figure 9). a) 3D Upper
 520 hemisphere stereographic projection of a $(001)_{Clt}$ plane inclined 60° to the substrate (i.e. $(100)_{Anh}$) in the XYZ coordinate
 521 system. The plane is rotated around the X-axis. Note $(001)_{Clt}$ pole (P) is the same in (b). b) Annotated $(001)_{Clt}$ pole figure
 522 showing angular dispersion of poles along X and Y-axes which correspond to textural components A and B,
 523 respectively. Along the X-axis density distribution is asymmetric with respect to YZ plane, suggesting a lesser
 524 development of crystals along -X axis. c) Development of textural component A on $(100)_{Anh}$ where progressive angular
 525 spreading occurs from $(001)_{Clt}$ parallel to $(100)_{Anh}$ (t_0) to $\pm 50^\circ$ around Y-axis (i.e. $\parallel [001]_{Anh}$; t_n). Only a pair of
 526 twinned crystals is represented for clarity, but a mirror pairs exist (see Figure 5b). d) Celestite textural component B is
 527 the result of a rotation of crystals oriented with $(001)_{Clt} \parallel (001)_{Anh}$ and $(210)_{Clt} \parallel (100)_{Anh}$ (indexed large crystal) up to
 528 $\pm 30^\circ$ around the X-axis (see Figure 5b).

529 Textural patterns of celestite overgrowths on $(001)_{Anh}$ are compatible with the progressive
 530 development of disoriented celestite subunits (Figure 11a). Textural component A represents
 531 celestite crystals oriented with $(001)_{Clt} \parallel (100)_{Anh}$ and $(210)_{Clt} \parallel (001)_{Anh}$. An accumulated
 532 rotation of $\pm 70^\circ$ around $\langle hk0 \rangle_{Clt}$ (e.g. $\langle 210 \rangle$), aligned to the X-axis, results into the textural

533 component B (Figures 11a and 11b) and the swan-like habit (Figure 6). In the $(210)_{\text{Ct}}$ pole figure
534 (Figure 11b) conical and cylindrical best fit is calculated for main point maxima, which is
535 indicative of a symmetry axis located around $\langle 210 \rangle$.⁵² The schematic drawing in Figure 11c
536 describes the substrate induced twinning of celestite crystals as interpreted from both, texture
537 results and SEM observations on $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$. In the $(210)_{\text{Ct}}$ pole figure (Figure 11b), two maxima
538 are projected near the X-axis (white and black triangles). These maxima most likely correspond
539 to the $(2-10)_{\text{Ct}}$ faces of the two populations of differently oriented swan-like aggregates related
540 through a mirror plane parallel to $(010)_{\text{Anh}}$ and whose coalesce leads to the formation of
541 substrate induced twins form, as depicted in Figure 6. A scheme of this type of twins, consistent
542 with the textural components derived from $(210)_{\text{Ct}}$ pole figure, is show in Figure 11c. In this
543 geometrical model two differently oriented celestite crystals (Stars 1 and 2), both with (210)
544 parallel to $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$, form a twin, with $(010)_{\text{Anh}}$ acting as the twin plane (parallel to Y-axis in Figure
545 11d). The simplified $(210)_{\text{Ct}}$ pole figure in Figure 11d shows the angular relationship between
546 relevant $(2-10)$ poles of crystals 1 and 2 (154.6°). This is consistent with the angular
547 measurement between equivalent $\langle 210 \rangle$ textural maxima in Figure 11b, where white and black
548 triangles define an angle of 152° . The proposed substrate induced twinning model reflects these
549 observations as well as the features of celestite aggregates as shown in Figure 6.

550

551 **Figure 11.** Model for celestite textural components developed on $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$. a) Development of celestite subunits by an
 552 accumulated rotation ($\pm 70^\circ$) of crystals primary oriented with $(001)_{\text{CIt}} // (100)_{\text{Anh}}$ and $(210)_{\text{CIt}} // (001)_{\text{Anh}}$ (i.e.
 553 component A) around an $\langle hk0 \rangle_{\text{CIt}}$ (e.g. $\langle 210 \rangle$), ca. X-axis. As a result, swan-like habit aggregates are generated (see
 554 Figure 6). b) $(210)_{\text{CIt}}$ pole figure where cylindrical (white line) and conical (white dashed line) best fit have been
 555 calculated for $(210)_{\text{CIt}}$ point maxima. Symmetry rotational axis in both cases falls around $\langle 210 \rangle_{\text{CIt}}$ maximum (white
 556 triangle). A conceptual sketch for a cylindrical best fit is included. Black triangle represents submaxima separated by
 557 152° of white triangle and correlate with $(2-10)_{\text{CIt}}$ poles as explained in c) and d). c) Geometrical model of two celestite
 558 crystals (starts 1 and 2) whose growth on $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ results in the formation of a substrate induced twin. The angular
 559 relationship between $(2-10)$ poles (in red) of these crystals (154.6°) is depicted. Note that these crystals are related by
 560 a mirror plane parallel to $(010)_{\text{Anh}}$. d) Simplified $(210)_{\text{CIt}}$ pole figure showing the projection of $(2-10)$ directions from
 561 crystal 1 (black triangle) and crystal 2 (white triangle). The twin plane will be parallel to YZ coordinate plane. Note the
 562 correlation with the real texture represented in b).

563

564

565 **Conclusions**

566 The interaction of anhydrite cleavage surfaces with Sr-bearing aqueous solutions leads to the
567 dissolution of the primary anhydrite and the concomitant nucleation of celestite. The structural
568 matching between the anhydrite substrate and the celestite overgrowth determines the
569 epitactic nature of the latter.

570 Two textural components have been identified in celestite aggregates growing on $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ and
571 $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$. These components represent the endmembers of the progressive development of
572 celestite epitactic growth on anhydrite planes, and correlate with the following symmetry
573 elements that belong to the anhydrite substrate:

574 - On $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$, component A shows celestite crystals with an initial orientation of $(001)_{\text{Clt}}$ parallel
575 to $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ and $\langle 120 \rangle_{\text{Clt}}$ parallel to $[001]_{\text{Anh}}$ and $[010]_{\text{Anh}}$. They correlate with the 4-fold twinned
576 crystals, whose constituting subunits rotate from $(001)_{\text{Clt}}$ parallel to $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ to $\pm 50^\circ$ around Y-
577 axis (i.e. // $[001]_{\text{Anh}}$). Component B is the result of a rotation of crystal subunit oriented with
578 $(001)_{\text{Clt}}$ parallel to $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$, and $(210)_{\text{Clt}}$ parallel to $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ up to $\pm 30^\circ$ around the X-axis.

579 - On $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$, component A is represented by celestite crystals primary oriented with $(001)_{\text{Clt}}$
580 parallel to $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$, and $(210)_{\text{Clt}}$ parallel to $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$. Component B is generated by progressive
581 misorientation of celestite subunits, with an accumulated rotation of $\pm 70^\circ$ around an $\langle hk0 \rangle_{\text{Clt}}$
582 axis (e.g. $\langle 210 \rangle$), approximately aligned to X-axis. The celestite aggregates that result from this
583 progressive subunit misorientation show a characteristic swan-like habit. In parallel, geometrical
584 relationships have been identified which are consistent with the development of substrate
585 induced twinning, with the mirror plane $(010)_{\text{Anh}}$ acting as the twin plane after coalescence of
586 differently oriented swan-like aggregates.

587 The strongest texture (F^2 -index) is recorded on $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$, followed by that on $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$. Texture
588 strength inversely correlates with the relative number of celestite crystals randomly oriented,

589 where $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ shows the largest number of crystals with a random orientation (0.48 m.r.d.).
590 Celestite texture on sample $(010)_{\text{Anh}}$ is consistent with it, resulting from a mixture of the textural
591 components derived from celestite overgrowths on step and edge pits, where $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ and
592 $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$ are exposed. Consequently, the development of this texture is not related to epitactic
593 growth on $(010)_{\text{Anh}}$ but on $(100)_{\text{Anh}}$ and $(001)_{\text{Anh}}$.

594 We attribute the development of the misorientational spreads involved in the formation of
595 celestite aggregates on anhydrite substrates to split growth phenomena induced by
596 incorporation of small amounts of Ca substituting Sr in celestite structure. This incorporation
597 would induce lattice strain which would be released through the formation of dislocations
598 spatially arranged at regular intervals in small-angle boundaries. The anisotropic development
599 of misorientational spreads observed in the swan-like celestite aggregates formed on (001)
600 anhydrite substrate could be due to differences in the amount of Ca incorporated in different
601 regions of celestite crystals depending on their relative proximity to the anhydrite substrate and
602 driven by the existence of compositional gradients at the boundary layer.

603 ***Acknowledgments***

604 This study was supported by the MINECO (Spain) under project CGL2016-77138-C2-1-P. PF
605 acknowledges a FPU predoctoral-contract (FPU17/01689) from the Spanish Ministry of Science,
606 Innovation and Universities. JGB appreciates financial support by the Spanish Ministry of Science
607 and Innovation through the IEDI-2016-00691 fellowship and the project CGL2016-78560-P of the
608 Spanish Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness. The texture experiments were
609 performed on beamline ID11 at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF), Grenoble,
610 France. JMSM and JGB are grateful to Carlotta Giacobbe at the ESRF for providing superb
611 assistance in using beamline ID11.

612

613

References

- 614 1. Kolasinski, K.W. *Surface Science: Foundations of Catalysis and Nanoscience*. John Wiley Sons, Ltd: England, **2002**,
615 305 pp.
- 616 2. Wagner, S. Epitaxy in solar cells. *J. Cryst. Growth*. **1975**, 31, 113-121.
- 617 3. Altree-Williams, A.; Pring, A.; Ngothai, Y.; Brugger, J. Textural and compositional complexities resulting from coupled
618 dissolution–reprecipitation reactions in geomaterials. *Earth-Sci. Rev.* **2015**, 150, 628-651.
- 619 4. Casella, L.A.; Griesshaber, E.; Yin, X.; Ziegler, A.; Mavromatis, V.; Müller, D.; Ritter, A.C.; Hippler, D.; Harper, E.M.;
620 Dietzel, M.; Immenhauser, A.; Schöne, B.R.; Angiolini, L.; Schmah, W.W. Experimental diagenesis: insights into
621 aragonite to calcite transformation of *Arctica islandica* shells by hydrothermal treatment. *Biogeosciences*. **2017**, 14,
622 1461-1492.
- 623 5. Gill, J. S.; Nancollas, G. H. The growth of gypsum crystals on barite and calcite. *Desalination*. **1979**, 29, 247-254.
- 624 6. Perdikouri, C.; Kasiotas, A.; Geisler, T.; Schmidt, B.C.; Putnis, A. Experimental study of the aragonite to calcite
625 transition in aqueous solution. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Ac.* **2011**, 75, 6211-6224.
- 626 7. Perdikouri, C.; Piazzolo, S.; Kasiotas, A.; Schmidt, B.C.; Putnis, A. Hydrothermal replacement of aragonite by calcite:
627 interplay between replacement, fracturing and growth. *Eur. J. Mineral.* **2013**, 25, 123-136.
- 628 8. Putnis, A. *Introduction to Mineral Sciences*. Cambridge University Press. **1992**, 457 pp.
- 629 9. Strens, R.G.J. Stability of Al_2SiO_5 solid solutions. *Mineral. Mag.* **1968**, 36, 839-849.
- 630 10. Chernov, A.A. Nucleation and epitaxy. In *Modern Crystallographic III: Crystal Growth*; Springer Series on Solid-State
631 Science 36.; Springer-Verlag: Berlin, **1984**; pp 48-103
- 632 11. Van der Merwe, J.H. Equilibrium structure of a thin epitaxial film. *J. Appl. Phys.* **1970**, 41, 4725-4731.
- 633 12. Van Der Merwe, J.H. The role of lattice misfit in epitaxy. *Crit. Rev. Solid State*. **1978**, 7, 209-231.
- 634 13. Copel, M.; Reuter, M.C.; Kaxiras, E.; Tromp, R.M. Surfactants in epitaxial growth. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **1989**, 63, 632.
- 635 14. Cuesta Mayorga, I.; Astilleros, J.M.; Fernández-Díaz, L.; Morales, J.; Prieto, M.; Roncal-Herrero, T.; Benning, L.G.
636 Epitactic overgrowths of calcite ($CaCO_3$) on anhydrite ($CaSO_4$) cleavage surfaces. *Cryst. Growth Des.* **2018**, 18, 1666-
637 1675.
- 638 15. Evans, M.M.R.; Glueckstein, J.C.; Nogami, J. Epitaxial growth of manganese on silicon: Volmer-Weber growth on the
639 Si (111) surface. *Phys. Rev.* **1996**, 53, 4000.
- 640 16. Müller, P.; Fach, A.; John, J.; Tiwari, A.N.; Zogg, H.; Kosterz, G. Structure of epitaxial PbSe grown on Si (111) and Si
641 (100) without a fluoride buffer layer. *J. Appl. Phys.* **1996**, 79, 1911-1916.
- 642 17. Morales, J.; Astilleros, J.M.; Fernández-Díaz, L.; Álvarez-Lloret, P.; Jiménez, A. Anglesite ($PbSO_4$) epitactic
643 overgrowths and substrate-induced twinning on anhydrite ($CaSO_4$) cleavage surfaces. *J. Cryst. Growth*. **2013**, 380,
644 130-137.
- 645 18. Sunagawa, I. *Crystals: Growth, Morphology, Perfection*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. **2005**, 295pp.
- 646 19. Sethmann, I.; Wang, J.; Becker, U.; Putnis, A. Strain-induced segmentation of magnesian calcite thin films growing on
647 a calcite substrate. *Cryst. Growth Des.* **2010**, 10, 4319-4326.
- 648 20. People, R.; Bean, J.C. Calculation of critical layer thickness versus lattice mismatch for Ge_xSi_{1-x}/Si strained-layer
649 heterostructures. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2010**, 47, 322-324.
- 650 21. Tiller, W.A. *The Science of Crystallization: Microscopic Interfacial Phenomena*. Cambridge University Press. **1991**, 391
651 p.p.

- 652 22. Dodson, B. W.; Tsao, J.Y. Relaxation of strained-layer semiconductor structures via plastic flow. *Appl. Phys. Lett.*
653 **1987**, 51, 1325-1327.
- 654 23. Marée, P.M.J.; Barbour, J.C.; Van der Veen, J.F.; Kavanagh, K.L.; Bulle-Lieuwma, C.W.T.; Vieggers, M.P.A. Generation
655 of misfit dislocations in semiconductors. *J. Appl. Phys.* **1987**, 62, 4413-4420.
- 656 24. Hull, R. and Bean, J.C. Misfit dislocations in lattice-mismatched epitaxial films. *Crit. Rev. Solid State.* **1992**, 17, 507-
657 546.
- 658 25. Fernández-Díaz, L.; Astilleros, J.M.; Pina, C.M. The morphology of calcite crystals grown in a porous medium doped
659 with divalent cations. *Chem. Geol.* **2006**, 225, 314-321.
- 660 26. Sangwal, K. Etching of crystals: theory, experiment and application. **2012**, Elsevier.
- 661 27. Ober, J. A. Strontium. *Mining Engineering.* **2003**, 55, 48-49.
- 662 28. Hanor, J.S. A model for the origin of large carbonate-and evaporite-hosted celestine (SrSO₄) deposits. *J. Sediment.*
663 *Res.* **2004**, 74, 168-175.
- 664 29. Palmer, D. Crystal Maker Crystal Maker Software Ltd Yarnton England. **2005**.
- 665 30. Barreiro, J. G.; Wenk, H.R.; Vogel, S. Texture and elastic anisotropy of a mylonitic anorthosite from the Morin Shear
666 Zone (Quebec, Canada). *J. Struc. Geol.* **2015**, 71, 100-111.
- 667 31. Hammersley, A.P.; Svensson, S.O.; Thompson, A. Calibration and correction of spatial distortions in 2D detector
668 systems. *Nucl. Instrum. Meth. A.* **1994**, 346, 312-321.
- 669 32. Lutterotti, L.; Matthies, S.; Wenk, H. R.; Schultz, A. S.; Richardson J.J.W. Combined texture and structure analysis of
670 deformed limestone from time-of-flight neutron diffraction spectra. *J. Appl. Phys.* **1997**, 81, 594-600.
- 671 33. Hawthorne, F.C.; Ferguson, R.B. Anhydrous sulphates; I, Refinement of the crystal structure of celestite with an
672 appendix on the structure of thenardite. *Can. Mineral.* **1975**, 13, 181-187.
- 673 34. Matthies, S.; Vinel, G.W. On the reproduction of the orientation distribution function of texturized samples from reduced
674 pole figures using the conception of a conditional ghost correction. *Phys. Status Solidi. B.* **1982**, 112, K111-K114.
- 675 35. Wenk, H.R.; Matthies, S.; Donovan, J.; Chateigner, D. BEARTEX: a Windows-based program system for quantitative
676 texture analysis. *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* **1998**, 31, 262-269.
- 677 36. Bunge, H. J. *Texture analysis in materials science: mathematical methods.* Elsevier. 2013.
- 678 37. Gómez Barreiro, J.; Lonardelli, I.; Wenk, H.R.; Dresen, G.; Rybacki, E.; Ren, Y.; Tomé, C. N. Preferred orientation of
679 anorthite deformed experimentally in Newtonian creep. *Earth Planet. Sc. Lett.* **2007**, 264, 188-207.
- 680 38. Lutterotti, L.; Vasin, R.; Wenk, H.R. Rietveld texture analysis from synchrotron diffraction images. I. Calibration and
681 basic analysis. *Powder Diffr.* **2014**, 29, 76-84.
- 682 39. Wenk, H.R.; Lutterotti, L.; Kaercher, P.; Kanitpanyacharoen, W.; Miyagi, L.; Vasin, R. Rietveld texture analysis from
683 synchrotron diffraction images. II. Complex multiphase materials and diamond anvil cell experiments. *Powder Diffr.*
684 **2014**, 29, 220-232.
- 685 40. Shindo, H.; Shitagami, K.; Kondo, S.; Seo, A. Atomic force microscopic observation of directional layer growth and
686 dissolution on surfaces of sulfate minerals. *J. Cryst. Growth.* **1999**, 198, 253-257.
- 687 41. Kostov, I.; Kostov, R.I. Crystal habits of minerals. Bulgarian Academic Monographs (1). Pensoft Publishers and Prof.
688 Marin Drinov Academic Publishing House. 1999.
- 689 42. Hartman, P.; Strom, C.S. Structural morphology of crystals with the barite (BaSO₄) structure: a revision and
690 extension. *J. Cryst. Growth.* **1989**, 97, 502-512.
- 691 43. Massaro, F.R.; Pastero, L.; Costa, E.; Sgualdino, G.; Aquilano, D. Single and Twinned Li₂CO₃ Crystals (Zabuyelite)
692 Epitaxially Grown on {0001} and {1014} Forms of CaCO₃ (Calcite) Crystals. *Cryst. Growth Des.* **2008**, 8, 2041-2046.

- 693 44. Shtukenberg, A.G.; Astilleros, J.M.; Putnis, A. Nanoscale observations of the epitaxial growth of hashemite on barite
694 (001). *Surf. Sci.* **2005**, 590, 212-223.
- 695 45. Pinto, A.J.; Jimenez, A.; Prieto, M. Interaction of phosphate-bearing solutions with gypsum: Epitaxy and induced
696 twinning of brushite (CaHPO₄·2H₂O) on the gypsum cleavage surface. *Am. Mineral.* **2009**, 94, 313-322.
- 697 46. Hull, D.; Bacon, D. J. *Introduction to dislocations* (Vol. 37). Elsevier, 2011.
- 698 47. Nindiyasari, F.; Griesshaber, E.; Fernandez-Díaz, L.; Astilleros, J. M.; Sanchez-Pastor, N.; Ziegler, A.; Schmahl, W.
699 W. Effects of Mg and hydrogel solid content on the crystallization of calcium carbonate in biomimetic counter-diffusion
700 systems. *Cryst. Growth Des.* **2014**, 14, 4790-4802.
- 701 48. Nindiyasari, F.; Fernández-Díaz, L.; Yin, X.; Greiner, M.; Griesshaber, E.; Tsige, M.; Ziegler, A.; Schmahl, W. W.
702 Influence of gel-strength and magnesium doping on the organization of calcite/hydrogel mesocrystal composites. *Eur.*
703 *J. Mineral.* **2019**, 31, 217-229.
- 704 49. Putnis, C.V.; Tsukamoto, K.; Nishimura, Y. Direct observations of pseudomorphism: compositional and textural
705 evolution at a fluid-solid interface. *Am. Mineral.* **2005**, 90, 1909-1912.
- 706 50. Ruiz-Agudo, E.; Putnis, C.V.; Putnis, A. Coupled dissolution and precipitation at mineral–fluid interfaces. *Chem. Geol.*
707 **2014**, 383, 132-146.
- 708 51. Ruiz-Agudo, E.; King, H.E.; Patiño-López, L.D.; Putnis, C.V.; Geisler, T.; Rodriguez-Navarro, C. Putnis, A. Control of
709 silicate weathering by interface-coupled dissolution-precipitation processes at the mineral-solution interface. *Geology.*
710 **2016**, 44, 567-570.
- 711 52. Allmendinger, R.W.; Cardozo, N.; Fisher, D.M. *Structural geology algorithms: Vectors and tensors*. Cambridge
712 University Press. 2011. 286 pp.

713

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure
10

Figure 11

Abstract
Graphic

